

Advancing Alternative Migration Governance

Profiles, drivers, journeys, protection and assistance challenges of people on the move towards Greece and Italy

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Mixed Migration Centre

2022

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Abstract

Between November 2019 and February 2022, the Mixed Migration Centre conducted 4Mi in Italy and Greece as part of the ADMIGOV project. 4Mi is a primary data collection system initiated in 2014, comprising an in-depth survey questionnaire targeting refugees and migrants on mixed migration routes and covering eight main research areas: profile, drivers of migration and intentions, the route and the journey, protection, assistance, smuggling, financing of the journey, and access to information. This report presents detail of the methodology as well as aggregate analysis of the data collected in Italy (995 interviews) and Greece (1,600), with disaggregation by nationality (people from Bangladesh, Pakistan, Sudan and a diverse group from West Africa interviewed in Italy, and people from Afghanistan, Democratic Republic of the Congo, Pakistan and Syria interviewed in Greece).

The report details a range of results and findings, reflecting the broad scope of the survey. Key findings relating to ADMIGOV's focus on protection are: that reliance on smugglers can increase the vulnerability of refugees and migrants; respondents faced a variety of risks; Libya and Turkey are reported as particularly dangerous places on the journey towards Europe; respondents who had reached Greece most often cited governmental authorities/police as perpetrators of violations and abuse, while those in Italy most often reported criminal gangs/militia; smugglers are also frequently perceived as perpetrators; respondents in both countries often reported a need for legal assistance, and in Greece, respondents frequently reported needs for psychological support and medical assistance.

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Introduction

This is a report about the experiences of people on the move who have arrived in Greece and Italy, presenting aggregate analysis of the data collected under the Admigov in 2020/2021 and offering some emerging top-line key findings.

1. Objective and scope of data collection

1.1 Purpose of the data collection

What we do and why: data collection among migrants and refugees in Europe

The Advancing Alternative Migration Governance (Admigov) project seeks to promote an alternative migration governance model, studying how alternative approaches to migration governance can be better designed and put into practice. A better understanding of what is happening in the ground, and the impact of current migration governance, will benefit this aim: to better understand why migrants and refugees are moving to Europe from other regions around the globe, what situations they encounter, why they do not stay in the countries they pass through, it is necessary to study their choices and how they intersect with policy.

The Danish Refugee Council's Mixed Migration Centre (MMC) therefore implemented its flagship primary data collection initiative on mixed migration – [4Mi](#) – within the framework of the Admigov project and conducted in-depth quantitative interviews with migrants and refugees on the move in Italy and Greece. 4Mi has allowed MMC, and Admigov, to gain direct insights into the experiences of people on the move toward Greece and Italy, including challenges and protection needs as well as the intentions of people travelling along mixed migration routes.

Why 4Mi?

Despite the high interest and concern around the rising phenomenon of mixed migration, policy formation, political debate and humanitarian programming are taking place in a context that often lacks concrete and robust data. One of the reasons for this is the challenges associated with collecting data about a mobile, heterogeneous, and hard-to-reach population spread across the globe. In this framework, identifying (and addressing) protection needs and challenges is particularly complex as many migrants and refugees are often “off the grid”, travelling by irregular means, and in a fragmented manner that makes it even harder to identify their basic needs and the risks they encounter on the way, and to investigate their intentions.

4Mi, as a regular, standardized, quantitative, globalized system of collecting primary data on mixed migration flows, aims at filling these information gaps by providing the largest, in-depth, globally comparable dataset, based on direct interviews with refugees and migrants along mixed migration routes around the world. 4Mi provides key insights for better knowledge, policy and programming on mixed migration and contributes towards more effective protection responses while providing an evidence base for decision-making.

Since 2014, when it first started in East Africa, MMC and 4Mi have expanded geographically and thematically, to count Europe, West Africa, East and Southern Africa, North Africa, Asia, and Latin America, as well as a global team in Geneva.

4Mi is currently the only program providing such rich, large-scale, in-depth information, capitalizing on being part of an international humanitarian NGO (the Danish Refugee Council), close cooperation with national civil society organizations and our large network of field enumerators.

4Mi in brief

- Continuous access to hard-to-reach populations
- Standardized methodology, combined with flexibility, adaptation & innovation
- Community-based enumerators
- Large-scale quantitative data, with rich insights offering the human face of mixed migration
- Large samples, allowing for advanced analysis
- Complementarity with other data collection systems

2. Methodology, ethics, sampling

2.1 Timeline of data collection

Data collection started in Italy and Greece in November 2019 and 48 months of continuous data collection was expected. The Covid-19 pandemic significantly slowed activities. Data collection was suspended from March 2020 to July 2020 due to movement restrictions in both countries. From July, data collection shifted to remote interviews (by phone) and sampling relied on referrals from third parties (enumerators received additional training to be able to do this). Starting January 2021, enumerators resumed face-to-face interviews in parallel with phone surveys. All this ultimately resulted in an extension of the timeline for data collection until December 2021 for Greece and February 2022 for Italy. See Section 2.2 for details of the number of surveys.

2.2 Sampling

As it is not possible to reliably estimate the size of 4Mi's population(s) of interest, and 4Mi sometimes targets specific groups of participants irrespective of population size, 4Mi utilizes non-probabilistic sampling. Specifically, 4Mi uses purposive sampling where potential participants are informally approached by 4Mi enumerators based on a small set of criteria. The geographic locations of data collection are determined by a mapping of where the target population is likely to be more concentrated. The careful selection of sites for data collection, and setting of targets to achieve diversity in sampling, means that while 4Mi data is not representative, and MMC cannot measure stocks, flows, and volumes, it is highly indicative and provides good information on the overall perceptions and experiences of the target population.

○ Location of data collection

MMC conducted 4Mi data collection in Italy and Greece, as primary entry points to Europe for migrants and refugees travelling along mixed migration routes.

During the inception phase of the project, specific project locations within each country were selected in order to be able to reach the population of interest.

In Greece, data collection was carried out mostly in Athens, where a large proportion of refugees and migrants travel through. Some interviews were conducted elsewhere, but participant recruitment proved challenging and the team focused on Athens for sampling. See below the number of interviews by location:

- **Athens:** 1,509 interviews
- **Thessaloniki:** 68 interviews
- **Ioannina:** 17 interviews
- **Other locations:** 6 interviews

Phone interviews: 506

Face to face: 1,094

Total: 1,600

In Italy, MMC collected 4Mi surveys across the country, including big cities and strategic places for migration routes. The full list of locations is below:

North (289 interviews):

- Emilia-Romagna: Modena
- Friuli-Venezia Giulia: Gorizia, Udine, Trieste
- Liguria: Ventimiglia
- Piedmont: Turin, Asti, Cuneo, Vercelli, Pinerolo, Novi Ligure, Alba, Savigliano

Centre (458 interviews):

- Latium: Rome, Imperia
- Tuscany: Arezzo, Livorno, Empoli, Florence

South and Islands (248 interviews):

- Apulia: Brindisi, Cassano delle Murge, Bari, Acquaviva delle Fonti
- Campania: Napoli
- Molise: Campobasso
- Sicily: Catania, Messina, Caltanissetta, Calatabiano, Milazzo, Milena, Sutera

Phone interviews: 168

Face to face: 827

Total: 995

- **Target groups**

4Mi's population of interest (the population from whom the sample is drawn) is composed of all refugees and migrants, irrespective of the causes for migration (war, economic, environmental, etc.). No distinction is made between economic migrants, asylum seekers and onward-moving refugees.

Within this population of interest, 4Mi specifically targeted adults travelling along mixed migration routes, who have crossed the border to the country of interview within the past 5 years,¹ and who are not on a return journey to their country of departure or origin. Participants must not have been interviewed by 4Mi before.

MMC's understanding of mixed migration

Mixed migration refers to cross-border movements of people including refugees fleeing persecution and conflict, victims of trafficking and people seeking better lives and opportunities. Motivated to move by a multiplicity of factors, people in mixed flows have different legal statuses as well as a variety of vulnerabilities. Although entitled to protection under international human rights law, they are exposed to multiple rights violations along their journey. Those in mixed migration flows travel along similar routes, using similar means of travel - often travelling irregularly and wholly or partially assisted by migrant smugglers.

In Greece, MMC originally targeted Syrians, Afghans and Iraqis travelling along the Eastern Mediterranean route, being the most represented nationalities for number of arrivals when the project started. However, during the course of the project, MMC expanded data collection to reach other nationalities which, even if not among the most frequent arrivals, were of interest because of information gaps. Interviews with Iraqis were therefore suspended, and Pakistanis and Congolese (DRC) were added to the sample.

In Italy, MMC originally focused on Nigerians, Pakistanis and Ivorians. However, in July 2020 sampling criteria were broadened to reach other nationalities. MMC interviewed West Africans (from Nigeria, Mali, Côte d'Ivoire, The Gambia, Senegal, Guinea, Ghana, Burkina Faso, Niger, Sierra Leone, Liberia, Togo, Benin), Central Africans (Cameroon, Chad, DRC) East Africans (Sudan, Eritrea, Ethiopia, Kenya, Somalia), North Africans (Libya, Morocco, Tunisia, Egypt) and Asians (Bangladesh, Pakistan, Afghanistan), as well as a very small number of other nationalities (Armenia, Georgia, Iraq, Turkey, Syria, totalling fewer than 10 respondents).

- **Limitations and mitigation measures**

Given the limitations of the sampling methods available, 4Mi's overall approach to sampling is to achieve diversity, and try to collect data on as many different profiles as possible within the target population, including in terms of gender, nationality, ethnicity, religion, location, route, etc.

¹ The length of stay in the town of interview was 2 years, while the length of stay in country of interview was 5 years.

4Mi has put in place a series of measures to limit and/or control for biases associated with the sampling method, including:

- thorough enumerator training
- recording of metadata relating to sampling and participant recruitment (e.g. place, referral mechanism, time of day);
- mapping and site selection for participant recruitment;
- enumerators' strong access to the refugee and migrant community; and
- robust data cleaning and validation procedures.

Limitations and Covid-19

Restrictions on movement during the Covid-19 pandemic meant that data collection was suspended for a short period. When it was resumed – still during movement restrictions – sampling methods were changed to enable remote participant recruitment (by telephone). This provided additional limitations in that it required participants to have access to a phone, and sampling relied more strongly on referrals.

2.3 Tools and modalities of data collection

○ 4Mi survey questionnaire

The 4Mi survey is the main instrument of 4Mi data collection. The questionnaire is administered either face-to-face or remotely, in an interview format. Enumerators administer the survey verbally, noting responses on their phones using ODK Collect data collection software. It is a structured questionnaire, with all but one question being closed-ended. Many answers are multi-select.

The 4Mi Migrant Survey covers 8 key areas:

1. Profile: socio-demographic data, including age, nationality, religion, sex, socio-economic status, etc.
2. Route and journey: country of departure, transit countries, places stopped and reasons why, etc.
3. Drivers: reasons for leaving, influences on migration decision-making, destination intentions, determination to reach destination, etc.
4. Protection risks²: perceived risks and dangerous locations, perpetrators, etc.
5. Assistance: type of assistance received, assistance providers, locations where assistance is most needed, etc.
6. Smuggling: services provided by smugglers, payments arrangements, perceptions of smugglers, etc.
7. Financing the journey: sums paid, access to money while travelling, bribes paid, etc.
8. Access to information: sources and media of information used before and during the journey, phone and internet access, social media use, etc.

To complement the information gathered through the above-mentioned sections with qualitative data, the survey contains an open-ended question where respondents can provide additional information and/or share details of their journey and experiences.

During the course of the project, minor amendments/updates were made to the survey to adjust it to the necessity of a remote data collection and telephone interviews. In March 2020, the Covid-19 pandemic obliged MMC to stop face-to-face participant recruitment and data collection. The resumption of data collection in July 2020 used the same survey with a few additional questions on the impact of the pandemic. From July 2020, data collection was primarily by telephone, but face to face where it was safe to do so. From

² For the purpose of 4Mi data collection protection risks are defined as death, physical violence, sexual violence, robbery, detention, kidnapping, bribery/extortion, non-physical violence (eg. harassment) and injury/ill-health from harsh conditions.

January 2021, a shorter version of the survey was implemented, recognising that the original, longer, survey was not well adapted to telephone interviews. This retained the key questions from the pre-2020 survey and continued to cover the same themes. It underwent minor adjustments to phrasing and answer options in September, after a review of the data collected. At each stage enumerators received training on the changes.

- **Implementation modalities (through implementing partners).**

MMC chose to conduct data collection through implementing partners who had an established presence on the ground and were already working within the refugee and migrant community, which facilitated access to the target population. Contracting took place through a tendering process in line with DRC's standard procedures, as well as existing MMC guidance on assessing and contracting partners for 4Mi data collection.

- **Field enumerators**

- a) Selection**

Field enumerators for this project were individuals often of the nationality of the refugees and migrants they interview, and refugees or migrants themselves, or local community members who had access to the target population. They either spoke the language of the people they interviewed or were otherwise assisted by cultural mediators speaking the language of the respondents. Enumerators recruited participants in urban centers, border areas, reception centers and similar locations where there was a large presence of the target population.

- b) Training**

A two-day enumerator training was held before data collection began, which covered:

- Introduction to MMC and 4Mi.
- Participant recruitment procedures.
- The 4Mi survey –, explaining it question by question, any nuances or pitfalls, responding to queries.
- Interview techniques and how to deal with potentially sensitive questions and answers.
- Ethics: trust and honesty, consequences of fraud or unethical behaviour, anonymity, confidentiality.
- DRC's Code of Conduct.
- Training in phone use, ODK setup and use, administration, submission of completed surveys in ONA etc.

All enumerators received a training package, with the tools and guidance to administer the survey in line with MMC's standards. They were also provided with a unique identifier, to be used in submitting surveys, and access to the online platform for data collection, [Ona](#). Additional refresh trainings were delivered to present survey revisions and the modalities of remote implementation. The following topics were covered:

- Modification to the survey with the additional Covid-19 questions;
- Remote participant recruitment and survey administration;
- Key messages on Covid-19, symptoms and treatment, and infection prevention and control, and how to deliver them.

- c) Management**

The implementing partners were tasked with the daily management of enumerators, including monitoring of data collection, organizing and issuing payments to enumerators, handling technical assistance etc. MMC retained direct responsibility for enumerator training and oversaw data cleaning and validation.

- **Data management**

- a) Data collection storage system (Ona)**

All 4Mi data was collected via smartphone and ODK Collect. Enumerators uploaded the surveys to an online data collection platform, Ona. Data was housed on servers in Europe. Access was controlled: enumerators only had permission to submit data; and only staff responsible for data validation and quality control had permission to access and download data. MMC developed specific standard operating procedures (SOPs) on how to set up projects in Ona, including formats and naming conventions, how to set up ODK Collect, and how to allocate the rights and permissions.

b) Data cleaning and validation

SOPs for 4Mi data validation identify and address potential fraud, anomalies, and errors. For this project, implementing partners conducted data cleaning and a first validation of data which was then double-checked by MMC staff. All feedback from validation was shared with the data collection partners in order to improve future performance.

c) Data protection

4Mi has SOPs to ensure data protection. 4Mi is anonymous and no directly identifiable data is collected, however there is a potential that a combination of data points could lead to indirect identification.

To ensure the safety and security of participants, these SOPs include the following measures, among others:

- Data collection is anonymous and confidential, and provided with fully informed consent.
- Anyone with access to raw data (enumerators, local partners and 4Mi staff) shall treat it as confidential. They can only use the data for the purposes of 4Mi and in the 4Mi name.
- Data is removed from enumerators' phones as soon as it has been safely uploaded to Ona.
- Access to data is restricted to those who need to use, and data is stored securely within DRC IT systems after download from Ona.
- Any data shared beyond MMC after collection is anonymised further to avoid identification (e.g. removal of location data). It is only shared if the use matches that for which participants gave their consent.

2.4 Ethical standards and requirements

Ethics are considered throughout every aspect of the 4Mi process. 4Mi is designed to hear directly from refugees and migrants, and ensure the full diversity of voices among the population on mixed migration routes is heard. The integrity, validity and reliability of our findings rely on adherence to the following ethical principles:

- Non-identification: all interviews are recorded anonymously. Datasets do not relate to any directly identifying characteristic of the participant.
- Respect for the autonomy, decision-making, and dignity of participants. MMC does not conduct data collection without fully informed consent, or the right to withdraw and to refuse.
- Beneficence: minimizing the risks and maximizing the benefits to participants. Protection, safety and security are all considered in making decisions on data collection, and are monitored closely throughout data collection. MMC does not collect data that it does not use.
- Justice: participants will be selected from groups of people whom the research may benefit.
- Respect for communities: protect and respect the values and interests of the community as a whole.

MMC's 4Mi staff all commit to the DRC Code of Conduct. The Code of Conduct is central to MMC staff's ethical practice, starting from the principle of *do no harm* and covering safety, legality, respect for human rights, and

conflicts of interests. The Code of Conduct is supplemented by these more research-related ethical considerations.

3. Project implementation

3.1 Relationship with implementing partners

MMC identified potential partners during an initial scoping exercise and put its requirements for a data collection out to tender. The tender process took place in line with DRC policy on procurement. Oxfam was selected in Italy and KMOP in Greece. Both contracts underwent a first amendment to adjust the timeline and schedule for delivery. The constraints imposed by Covid-19-related measures meant that, particularly in Italy, data collection faced significant obstacles. The contract with Oxfam was amended another three times, and ultimately the number of interviews delivered was reduced from 1,600 to 986, and compensation was reduced to reflect this. The contract with KMOP was extended to end 2021 rather than November, to enable them to reach the required number of surveys.

4. 4Mi Data analysis

4.1 The dataset

MMC is presenting an analysis of the data collected by country of interview and nationality of respondent. MMC has chosen not to use data collected from nationalities – or regional groupings of nationalities – for which numbers were low (for Italy, this includes people from East and Central Africa, North Africa, and Afghans, and for Greece this includes Iraqis). Most groups reached Italy via the Central Mediterranean Route; the group of Pakistanis all arrived via the Western Balkan Route. Respondents all reached Greece via the Eastern Route.

Note that in some disaggregations the sample size is small and results should be read with caution.

Greece (1,590 interviews)*	Italy (887 interviews)*
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Afghans (954) • Syrians (321) • Pakistani (175) • Democratic Republic of Congo (140) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • West Africans (549): Nigeria 200, Mali 100, Côte d'Ivoire 65, The Gambia 61, Senegal 51, Guinea 39, Ghana 9, Burkina Faso 7, Niger 6, Sierra Leone 5, Liberia 3, Togo 2, Benin 1 • Sudanese (100) • Bangladeshi (109) • Pakistani (129)

*Note the total number of interviews used in the analysis is lower than those collected, due to discarding during data validation.

4.2 Greece

4.2.1 Nationality, age and gender

n = 1590

Figure 1. Nationalities

n = 1590

Figure 3. Gender composition

Figure 2. Age ranges

n = 1590

- Of 1,590 surveys conducted in Greece between November 2019 and December 2021, the majority were with Afghans (60%). Most people were between 25 and 34 years of age. Almost half of Syrians and Afghans interviewed were women (40% and 45% respectively), while female Congolese and Pakistanis accounted for 17% and 19% of the sample, respectively.
- Interviews were conducted both face-to-face (1084) and by phone (506), mostly in Athens and Thessaloniki
- Almost half of Congolese (46%), Afghans (47%) and Syrians (45%) interviewed arrived in Italy in 2019 while Pakistanis' arrivals are more spread across 2016-2020 (between 11% and 23% every year).

4.2.2 Level of education

Figure 4. Level of education

Figure 5. Level of education (Afghans)

- The majority of respondents had completed primary or secondary education with Afghans more often (34%) reporting not having completed any level of education compared to other nationalities. Few mentioned having completed university.
- Syrian and Afghan women slightly more often reported having completed university compared to men.

Figure 6. Level of education (Syrians)

4.2.3 Professional background

n = 907

Figure 7. Working sector

Figure 8. Working sector (Afghans)

Figure 9. Working sector (Syrians)

- A majority of Congolese (70%), Afghans (60%) and Syrians (55%) were making money before leaving while Pakistanis more commonly reported not having a source of income (46%).
- Small business/trade is the main working sector for all respondents, followed by health workers for Syrians (17%) and Pakistanis (17%), driver/transportation for Afghans (20%) and civil service / teaching for Congolese (14%).
- Afghan women more often reported civil service/teaching (22% vs 3%) and domestic work (19% vs 14%) compared to men who more commonly reported small business/trade (23% vs 11%), agriculture/pastoralism/fishing (15% vs 1%).
- Syrian women more often reported finance/IT (14% vs 4%), domestic work (17% vs 4%), health work (17% vs 4%), and civil service/teaching (29% vs 4%), while men mostly worked in small business (29% vs 14%), and industry/manufacturing (22% vs 3%).

4.2.4 Drivers

n = 1590

Figure 10. For what reasons did you leave (aggregate)?

Figure 11. For what reasons did you leave?

Question is multiselect

- From the data, it is clear how complex and intertwined migration drivers are. With some differences across nationalities, the main reasons for leaving the country of origin were 1) violence, insecurity and conflict, 2) rights and freedom, 3) economic reasons, 4) personal or family reasons.
- Pakistanis more often mentioned violence (51%) and economic drivers (67%). Violence-related drivers together with rights and freedoms were predominant for Syrians (78% and 49%) and Afghans (66% and 62%). Congolese respondents reported a striking multiplicity of drivers: rights and freedom (89%) followed by violence (82%), access to service (78%) and economic drivers (74%).
- Access to services, while mainly reported by Congolese is also mentioned quite frequently by Pakistani (45%) and Afghan (42%) respondents.
- Women more frequently reported personal or family reasons.

4.2.5 Drivers: Economic reasons

n = 779

Figure 12. Economic reasons

Question is multiselect

- Among the economic-related drivers, unemployment or not earning enough were the main drivers, and often a combination of both.
- Congolese more often reported difficulties in doing business compared to other nationalities (34%).
- Afghan and Syrian men more often reported not making enough money (71% and 53%) while women more often reported being unemployed (37% and 59%).

Figure 13. Economic reasons (Afghans)

Figure 14. Economic reasons (Syrians)

4.2.6 Drivers: Reasons related to violence

- Among the violence-related drivers, for all respondents the main drivers were war/armed conflict/terrorism, and crime and general insecurity and political unrest/riots.
- Most respondents mentioned a combination of violence-related drivers. Congolese mostly reported crime/general insecurity (93%), political unrest/riots (90%) and war/armed conflict/terrorism (70%).
- SGBV was almost equally reported by Afghan men and women.

4.2.7 Drivers: Rights- and freedom-related reasons

Sexual discrimination was relevant for all but Afghans; it was the main driver for Syrian women (63%).

Question is multiselect

4.2.8 Drivers: Other reasons

- Access to health services and educational opportunities were more often reported general access to services such as infrastructure or transport, or corruption.
- Corruption within the government was reported more by Pakistanis (51%) and Afghans (55%)

- Respondents from all nationalities often mentioned family reunification or reunification with other family/friends abroad, cited by 92% of Congolese and 72% of Afghans who reported family reasons.
- 41% of Afghans mentioned domestic violence, and only slightly more often by women compared to men (44% vs 37%).

4.2.9 Decision making and influences

- 86% of Congolese and 61% of Syrians mentioned being influenced in their decision to migrate while Pakistanis and Afghans were partially influenced in their decision to migrate (47% and 51%).

- Personal connections, mostly friends/family (in country of departure and origin) and parents are the main reported influences for all nationalities.

- Congolese were heavily influenced in their decision to migrate from social media (72%) and mainstream media (48%) compared to all other nationalities.

- Afghan and Syrian women more often than men reported being influenced. The main reported influence for Afghan and Syrian women were their spouse (58% and 64%) while men were more commonly influenced by other family/friends

Figure 27. Did anyone influence your decision to migrate?

Figure 28. Did anyone influence your decision to migrate (Syrians)

Figure 29. Did anyone influence your decision to migrate (Afghans)

4.2.10 Alternatives to irregular migration

n = 1590 **Figure 30. Did you think there were things that you could do, which might address the reasons you gave for leaving?**

The majority of Pakistanis (75%), Syrians (65%) and Afghans (68%) did not think there were things they could do to avoid migrating in the way they did.

Conversely, the majority of Congolese respondents did think there were alternatives (72%). Those that they tried were mainly moving to another city (77%) and migrating abroad regularly (77%).

n = 468 **Figure 31. What did you try?**

Question is multiselect

4.2.11 Current status and future intentions

- Greece is not a final destination for respondents: indeed, the vast majority of respondents reported not having reached the end of the journey. Germany is the preferred destination for the majority of the respondent.
- Despite this, a majority reported their status as refugee or asylum seeker. Although respondents do not see a future in Greece they still have applied/are applying for asylum.

4.2.12 Assistance during the journey

n = 1590

Figure 35. Did you receive assistance?

n = 458

Figure 36. What kind of assistance did you receive?

n = 458

Figure 37. Who did you receive assistance from?

Question is multiselect

- A minority of respondents reported having received assistance on the journey.
- Among those who received assistance, the main assistance provided was basic relief: food, water, clothing and shelter.
- The majority of respondents received assistance from NGOs/UN agencies; almost half (48%) mentioned assistance received from the government

4.2.13 Assistance needs in Greece

Sample is smaller because question was added later on

- The majority of respondents needed assistance at the time of interview.
- Among those who need assistance, the majority said they need legal assistance, followed by psychosocial support and medical assistance.
- Very few require assistance related to integration (access to work/education) which might be related to the fact Greece is considered just a transit country even if people end up staying for longer periods.

4.2.14 Smuggling: did you use a smuggler?

n = 1587

Figure 40. Did you use a smuggler?

n = 1560

Figure 41. What did the smuggler provide you with?

- Almost all respondents used a smuggler(s) at some point during the journey despite almost all being refugees/asylum seekers.
- 82% of respondents used a smuggler for more than one activity/service.
- 48% of Congolese mentioned using one smuggler for the entire journey while the others more often used several different smugglers for different parts of the journey.
- Afghan (9% vs 4%) and Syrian (19% vs 8%) men more commonly used one smuggler for only part of the journey.
- Almost all respondents mentioned that smugglers provided transit across border yet other services were provided. Pakistanis, Syrians and Afghans often cited food and water, accommodation and in-country transportation while Congolese (66%) most commonly cited provision of documents.

4.2.15 Smuggling: risk or opportunity?

- Majority of Afghans (59%), Syrians (57%) and Pakistanis (59%) considered that the smuggler(s) helped them in achieving their goal of migrating to another country but, at the same time, they agreed/strongly agreed that they were intentionally misled by them.
- Congolese had a less positive opinion of smugglers with only 37% of them agreeing that the smuggler(s) helped them in reaching their goal, but equally, fewer 35% believed that a smuggler has misled them.

4.2.16 Financing the journey: sources

n = 1587

Figure 44. How did you initially finance your journey?

n = 954

Figure 45. How did you initially finance your journey? (Afghans)

n = 320

Figure 46. How did you initially finance your journey (Syrians)

- People financed their journey through a range of different means and Congolese respondents more often reported using multiple methods.
- Syrians and Afghans mostly used own funds (38% and 40%), sold assets (34% and 31%) or were supported by the family (30% and 32%).
- Afghan (37%) and Syrian (38%) women more often relied on the support of their family or had not paid anything at the beginning (23% and 29%).

4.2.17 Financing the journey: challenges *en route*

- For most people (75%-89% of Pakistanis, Afghans, Syrians) this was enough money for the journey but for 70% of Congolese it was not, and 63% of them could not get more money.
- Lack of financial resource, especially for Congolese, is likely to increase vulnerability as people get into debt or depend on smugglers.

Figure 48. How have you paid for the journey since then?

4.2.18 Information pre-departure

Questions are multiselect

- A majority of respondents (never less than 62%) report that they obtained information before the journey.
- The most frequent sources were family/friends (both in country of departure and elsewhere) and smugglers. Excepting Pakistanis, who less frequently mentioned family/friends in country of departure (15%)

- A majority of respondents also reported that they obtained information during the journey.
- Reliance on family/friends decreases after departure, apart from among Congolese.
- Reliance on smugglers remains high while the role of other migrants and local people increases.
- The role of online communication also increases especially for Syrians (41%) and Congolese (52%) .
- 36% of Congolese mentioned wider diaspora.
- NGOs/UN agencies were reported by Congolese (28%), Syrians (15%) and Afghans (15%), while only 2% of Pakistanis referred to them.

4.2.19 Means of information before and during the journey

Figure 51. Means of information before journey

Figure 52. Means of information during your journey

Questions are multiselect

- There are no major differences in means of obtaining information before and during the journey.
- Both before and during the journey respondents heavily rely on social media/messaging and in-person conversation. Afghans cited frequently also phone calls (41%) while Congolese mentioned websites (51%) more than others do.

4.2.20 Reliability of information

- For Pakistanis (33%), Syrians (30%), and Afghans (30%) friends/family in another country are the most reliable source of information, while Congolese considered other migrants as the most reliable source.
- 49% of Pakistanis would have not started the journey knowing what they know now, while in contrast 81% of Congolese would still have undertaken the journey, and 67% of Syrians.

Question is multiselect

4.2.21 Effects of Covid-19 on migration

Figure 55. How Covid-19 has affected life and migration experience

n = 701

- Most respondents of all nationalities mentioned being stuck in one place as a common effect of Covid-19, although to a lesser extent for Pakistanis (39%).
- For many, migration became more difficult because of border restrictions, especially Congolese (71%) and Afghans (50%).
- Congolese more often mentioned having fewer resettlement options (71%), being unable to afford basic goods or rent (30%) and lacking resources to finance the journey (40%).

Question is multiselect

4.2.22 Routes and conditions³

Map 1. Reported location of stops along the EMR and WBR

³ For the routes and protection analysis on the data collected in Greece, MMC focused on movements along the Eastern Mediterranean and the Western Balkan route. For this reason, Pakistani respondents interviewed in Greece (n= 175) were merged Pakistani respondents interviewed in Italy (n=129), amounting to 304 respondents.

4.2.23 Routes and conditions: reasons for stopping

Figure 56. Afghans reasons for stopping per location

Figure 57. Syrians reasons for stopping per location

n= number of times the place was indicated

Question is multiselect

Note: when respondents indicated “other” in Syria, they mostly referred to Smugglers’ activities such as dealing with border authorities or waiting to gather a bigger group of migrants

Figure 58. Pakistani reasons for stopping per location

n= number of times the place was indicated

Question is multiselect

Figure 59. Congolese reasons for stopping per location

n= number of times the place was indicated

Question is multiselect

Note: when respondents indicated "other" in Uganda, they mostly referred to applying and waiting for Visa release to Turkey

- Almost all (95%) respondents entered Greece through Turkey, but before the Turkey leg the picture varies considerably. Half of the respondents transited Iran. Syrians mostly transited only Turkey before reaching Greece. Two-thirds of Afghans crossed Iran—some started their journey in Iran—while some also crossed Pakistan (24%). Pakistanis, like Afghans, primarily crossed through Iran (82%) before reaching Turkey. Almost all Congolese (98%) flew to Turkey, but some flew from other countries (26% transited Uganda, and 19% Tanzania).
- Afghan, Pakistani and Syrian respondents most often mentioned the same three reasons for selecting the route: the smuggler chose it (41%, 46%, 25%, respectively); it was the only option (31%, 39%, 28%); and family/friends suggested it/were taking it (26%, 27%, 30%). While more Congolese respondents reported that family/friends suggested it/were taking it (56%), they also mentioned that that it was the route they knew best (54%) or the cheapest (37%).
- Of the 129 Pakistani respondents surveyed in Italy, 126 started their journey in Pakistan, 88% crossed Turkey, and 67% crossed Greece. A majority crossed Serbia, Croatia, and Slovenia, with many also crossing Bosnia and Herzegovina and North Macedonia. Some travelled through other neighboring countries, and a few reported having transited countries further north, including Hungary (11%) and Austria (7%), indicating a much more circuitous route.
- Most stops occurred in Turkey and Iran—the countries most transited. Overall, the main reasons for stopping were to wait for transport, rest, and the onward migration journey being blocked by authorities.

4.2.24 Protection – risks and perpetrators

Figure 60. Perceived risks on the EMR reported by Afghan respondents, by country / area

	n	Death	Physical violence	Sexual violence	Detention	Kidnap-ping	Robbery	Bribery/ extortion	Non-physical violence	Other
Pakistan	89	48%	78%	35%	56%	44%	72%	1%	1%	11%
Iran	653	64%	66%	31%	65%	26%	52%	4%	1%	20%
Turkey	877	33%	53%	34%	69%	16%	35%	3%	0%	15%
Mediterranean Sea	150	96%	57%	7%	59%	1%	9%	3%	0%	4%
Greece	126	19%	69%	7%	38%	1%	56%	4%	0%	66%

Note: 'Refused' all below 1%. 'Other' for Greece is mainly pushbacks at the border. The category 'injury / ill-health / conditions on the route' does not appear because it was not reported.

Figure 61. Perceived perpetrators of abuse and violations on the EMR reported by Afghan respondents, by country / area

	n	Criminals/ criminal gangs	Armed groups/ militias	Smugglers	Government officials	Other migrants	Family members	Other
Afghanistan	35	31%	3%	14%	80%	0%	3%	3%
Pakistan	89	67%	45%	19%	65%	18%	0%	3%
Iran	653	47%	33%	32%	82%	19%	2%	4%
Turkey	877	40%	20%	55%	66%	33%	4%	0%
Mediterranean Sea	150	43%	60%	32%	81%	1%	9%	6%
Greece	126	13%	5%	9%	87%	13%	0%	6%

Note: 'Refused' and 'don't know' all 1% or lower.

Figure 62. Perceived risks on the EMR reported by Syrian respondents, by country / area

	n	Death	Physical violence	Sexual violence	Detention	Kidnap-ping	Robbery	Bribery/ extortion	Injury / ill health / conditions	Non-physical violence	Other
Turkey	226	29%	43%	8%	59%	4%	22%	13%	5%	5%	14%
Mediterranean Sea	77	79%	8%	0%	44%	3%	4%	3%	1%	4%	23%
Greece	83	17%	52%	8%	43%	2%	37%	8%	0%	2%	43%

Note: 'Refused' all below 1%. 'Other' for Greece is mainly pushbacks at the border; other for Mediterranean is mainly shipwrecks.

Figure 63. Perceived perpetrators of abuse and violations on the EMR reported by Syrian respondents, by country / area

	n	Criminals/ criminal gangs	Armed groups/ militias	Smugglers	Government officials	Other migrants	Family members	Other
Turkey	226	20%	8%	42%	73%	15%	0%	0%
Mediterranean Sea	77	22%	21%	31%	62%	8%	0%	0%
Greece	83	29%	8%	6%	80%	29%	0%	0%

Note: 'Refused' and 'don't know' all 1% or lower.

Figure 64. Perceived risks on the EMR reported by Congolese respondents, by country / area

	n	Death	Physical violence	Sexual violence	Detention	Kidnap-ping	Robbery	Bribery/ extortion	Injury / ill health / condi-tions	Non-physical violence	Other
Turkey	95	19%	64%	22%	85%	9%	53%	59%	21%	42%	7%
Mediterranean Sea	100	85%	45%	2%	73%	2%	18%	36%	24%	35%	3%
Greece	64	17%	92%	52%	48%	5%	72%	39%	0%	25%	6%

Note: 'Refused' all below 1%.

Figure 65. Perceived perpetrators of abuse and violations on the EMR reported by Congolese respondents, by country / area

	n	Criminals/ criminal gangs	Armed groups/ militias	Smugglers	Government officials	Other migrants	Family members	Other
Turkey	95	72%	31%	57%	91%	40%	0%	0%
Mediterranean Sea	100	60%	40%	64%	84%	25%	0%	5%
Greece	64	64%	13%	22%	59%	89%	0%	3%

Note: 'Refused' and 'don't know' all below 1%.

Figure 66. Perceived risks on the EMR reported by Pakistani respondents, by country / area

	n	Death	Physical violence	Sexual violence	Detention	Kidnap-ping	Robbery	Bribery/ extortion	Injury / ill health / condi-tions	Non-physical violence	Other
Iran	206	72%	45%	3%	34%	14%	24%	3%	1%	0%	27%
Turkey	174	28%	40%	9%	45%	25%	21%	3%	2%	1%	12%
Mediterranean Sea	22	82%	23%	0%	9%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	5%
Greece	88	13%	74%	1%	50%	1%	27%	0%	1%	1%	78%
Balkans	40	28%	78%	3%	40%	13%	43%	10%	10%	0%	5%

Note: 'Refused' all below 1%. 'Other' in Greece mainly relates to pushbacks and confiscation of property.

Figure 67. Perceived perpetrators of abuse and violations on the EMR reported by Pakistani respondents, by country / area

	n	Criminals/ criminal gangs	Armed groups/ militias	Smugglers	Government officials	Other migrants	Family members	Other
Iran	206	17%	10%	19%	80%	2%	0%	7%
Turkey	174	12%	8%	47%	52%	7%	0%	9%
Mediterranean Sea	22	14%	9%	41%	45%	18%	0%	0%
Greece	88	5%	2%	3%	78%	2%	0%	8%
Balkans	40	25%	18%	20%	60%	13%	0%	10%

Note: 'Refused' and 'don't know' all 1% or below, except 3% 'don't know' for the Balkans.

4.2.25 Protection: dangerous locations

Map 2. Locations perceived as dangerous on the EMR and WBR (A)

Map 2. Locations perceived as dangerous on the EMR and WBR (B)

- Turkey and Iran are the most frequently transited countries on the EMR-WBR. They are also far more frequently reported to be dangerous: Places in Turkey are considered dangerous by 92% of Afghan respondents, 70% of Syrians, 68% of Congolese, and 57% of Pakistanis. The most often cited locations are Istanbul, Izmir, and Edirne. Iran is considered dangerous by 68% of Afghan and 68% of Pakistani respondents (with Afghans mostly reporting West Azerbaijan, and Pakistanis providing a range of less specific answers about locations). Greece itself is considered dangerous by 46% of Congolese, 29% of Pakistanis, 26% of Syrians, and 13% of Afghans. The Mediterranean is considered dangerous by 71% of Congolese, 24% of Syrians, 16% of Afghans and 7% of Pakistanis, percentages that are much lower than those for the much-longer and more dangerous Central Mediterranean crossing.
- Afghan respondents reported Turkey more frequently as a risky place for a range of incidents—mainly detention and physical violence, but also death, sexual violence, and robbery. The risk of detention was the most mentioned in Bodrum (86% of those who found it dangerous) and Edirne (84%). Iran was more commonly perceived to pose a risk of death, physical violence, and detention: detention was reported among 73% of those who mentioned West Azerbaijan. Sistan and Baluchestan was considered to pose risks of detention (74% of those who reported it as dangerous), physical violence (71%), and kidnapping (63%). Sexual violence was frequently mentioned in Bodrum (58%) and Van (59%) in Turkey. Finally, most of the “other” risks reported by Afghans in Greece were described as pushbacks at the border.
- Syrian respondents perceived incidents such as physical violence and detention in Turkey and Greece to be less common than Afghans. Risks of detention were reported to be high in Istanbul (79%) and Izmir (60%) in Turkey, and in Alexandroupoli (88%) in Greece.
- By contrast, a large majority of Congolese respondents who reported Turkey as dangerous mentioned detention and physical violence, and their figure for physical violence in Greece was even higher. Overall, Congolese reported more risks.
- Pakistani respondents had a common concern about death in Iran as well as crossing the Mediterranean. In Greece and the Balkans, the concern was more around physical violence, although, as for Afghans, a majority mentioned pushbacks and violations at the border to Greece (categorized as “other”). Detention was a fairly common concern across countries.
- Afghan respondents consistently reported state agents—such as border guards, immigration officials, police, and military personnel—as the main perpetrators of abuse. Only in Pakistan was another group more frequently mentioned: criminals/gangs. In Turkey, a majority mentioned smugglers too, while armed groups/militias were also reported in the Mediterranean (60%), possibly related to the reports about unidentified armed men pushing back refugees and migrants at sea between Greece and Turkey.
- Syrians also mentioned government officials more frequently, especially in Turkey, where they also often (42%) mentioned smugglers.
- Congolese respondents more frequently mentioned a more diverse array of perpetrators, more frequently reporting criminals and criminal gangs, smugglers, and other migrants, particularly in Greece. This may relate to reports of inter-communal violence in migrant reception centers.
- Pakistani respondents also reported government officials far more frequently as perpetrators of abuse, especially in Iran and Greece.

4.3 Italy

4.3.1 Nationality, age and gender

Figure 68. Nationalities

Figure 70. Gender

Figure 69. Age ranges

- Of 887 surveys conducted in Italy between November 2019 and February 2022, the majority were with West Africans. Almost half of respondents were under 25 years of age, and 91% were under 35. The majority were men. 19% of West African respondents were women. The unbalanced gender ratio in the sample may be at least in part due to men being easier to reach or more willing to be interviewed.
- Interviews were conducted both face-to-face (724) and by phone (163), across Italy (north, centre and south).
- The majority of Sudanese interviewed (74%) arrived in Italy in 2021. Most Bangladeshi (74%) arrived between 2020 and 2020; Pakistanis (83%) between 2018-2020 and 90% of West Africans between 2016 and 2019.

4.3.2 Level of education

The majority of respondents had completed primary or secondary education, with Pakistanis more often reporting having a secondary level of education (56%) compared to the other nationalities. A small percentage had completed university.

West African women had not received as much schooling: they more often reported having a non religious primary level of education (40% vs 30%) or no education at all (21% vs 15%). More men than women reported having completed secondary school (37% vs 31%).

4.3.3 Professional background

Figure 73. Working sector

n=582

Figure 74. Working sector (West Africans)

n=363

Figure 75. Where you making money before leaving?

- Most respondents were making money before leaving towards Europe yet a high percentage of Sudanese were unemployed (41%).
- Agriculture/pastoralism/fishing and small business are among the main sectors for all respondents, alongside small businesses. For Sudanese, the main sector is construction, cited by 29% of respondents.
- For West African women, small businesses and domestic work are the main areas of employment (32% and 25%).

4.3.4 Drivers

n=887

Figure 76. For what reasons did you leave?

Question is multiselect

- Overall, the main reasons for leaving the country of origin were: 1) violence, insecurity and conflict, 2) economic reasons, 3) personal or family reasons, and 4) rights and freedom. Most people mention more than one reason.
- Sudanese (77%), Pakistanis (56%) and West Africans (45%) most often mentioned violence, insecurity and conflict, while Bangladeshis (61%) mentioned economic reasons.
- Among West Africans, the top reason among women was personal and family reasons (50%, compared to 32% for men). Otherwise, there was little difference between genders.

4.3.5 Drivers: Economic reasons and reasons related to violence

Figure 77. Economic reasons

Figure 78. Reasons related to violence

Questions are multiselect

- Among the economic-related drivers, over half of Bangladeshis and West Africans mentioned not earning enough money.
- Among the violence-related drivers, war/armed conflict/terrorism was most frequent among Pakistanis (57%) and Sudanese (86%). West Africans reported both this and crime and general insecurity to an equal degree.
- 54% of West African women who reported violence as a driver, reported SGBV as violence-related driver, far higher than other violence-related drivers.

n=247

Figure 79. Reasons related to violence (West Africans)

- Overall, the main reported migration drivers were: 1) violence, insecurity and conflict (48%), 2) economic reasons (36%), 3) personal or family reasons (31%), and 4) rights and freedom (29%).
- Sudanese (77%), Pakistanis (56%) and West Africans (45%) most often mentioned violence/insecurity/ conflict, while Bangladeshis (61%) most often mentioned economic reasons.
- 54% of West African women who reported violence as a driver, reported SGBV, far higher than other violence-related drivers.
- 63% of respondents indicated more than one driver.

4.3.6 Decision making and influences

n=887 **Figure 80. Did anyone or anything influence your decision to migrate?**

- 86% of Sudanese mentioned not being influenced in their decision to migrate while all other nationalities were partially influenced. West African women reported being influenced more often than men (59% vs 37%).
- Personal connections, mostly friends/family in country of departure and parents, are the main reported influences for all nationalities. West African women less frequently report their parents as influential (23% compared to 45% of men who said anything/anyone influence them), but a majority talk about friends and family (68%), and a large proportion refer to smugglers (38% vs 5%).

Figure 81. Who influenced your decision to migrate?

n=224 **Figure 82. Who influenced your decision to migrate? (West Africans)**

4.3.7 Current status and future intentions

Figure 83. Migration status

Figure 84. Migration status (West Africans)

Figure 85. Have you reached the end of your journey?

- The majority of respondents (77% of Bangladeshis, 80% of Pakistanis and 70% of West Africans) said they had reached the end of their journey. Sudanese were an exception. Their preferred destinations were most often the UK (52%) and France (18%).
- There is an interesting correlation with migration status: respondents from Pakistan, Bangladesh and West Africa are mostly asylum seekers or refugees (92%, 71%, 67%), and the majority of Sudanese have irregular status (75%).
- Among West Africans, women more commonly than men have refugee status (45% vs 20%), while men more often have temporary residency (13% vs 4%). However, West African women represent a small part of the sample (19%) which calls for caution when interpreting presented results.
- Among those whose journey has ended in Italy, for the majority Italy is their preferred destination, however a minority in each group (14%-17%) have ended their journey in Italy without it being their preferred destination.

4.3.8 Assistance during the journey

- A minority of respondents reported having received assistance on journey.
- Among those who received assistance, the main assistance provided was basic relief: food, water and shelter.
- 49% of Pakistanis also received clothing and 33% medical assistance while Bangladeshis mostly received shelter (61%).

Figure 87. What kind of assistance did you receive (West Africans)?

Question is multiselect

Figure 88. What kind of assistance did you receive?

Sample is smaller because question was added later

4.3.9 Assistance needs in Italy

Figure 90. What kind of additional assistance do you need (West Africans)?

- A minority needed assistance at the time of interview, except Sudanese.
- Among those who need assistance, the majority of Sudanese said they needed cash, followed by a small number saying they need assistance for resettlement. West Africans in need sought legal assistance.
- The majority of those who mentioned “other” referred to support in finding a job.

4.3.10 Smuggling: did you use a smuggler?

n=882

Figure 91. Did you use a smuggler?

n=547

Figure 92. Did you use a smuggler (West Africans)

n=484

Figure 93. How did you pay the smuggler (West Africans)

- A large majority of respondents used a smuggler(s) at some point during the journey, most often several for different parts of the journey.
- Among West Africans who used a smuggler, women more commonly used one smuggler for the entire journey (45% vs 15%) while men more frequently used several for different parts of the journey (47% vs 30%) or one for only one part of the journey (28% vs 16%).
- While the majority of all nationalities paid the smuggler in instalments, with only Bangladeshis paying the smuggler almost equally in instalments (40%) and full before departure (38%), West African women paid in a range of modalities, including 19% who had not paid the smuggler.

4.3.11 Smuggling: what did the smuggler provide you with?

Figure 94. What did the smuggler provide you with?

Question is multiselect

4.3.12 Smuggling: risk or opportunity?

- A majority agreed that the smuggler had helped them achieve their migration goal – although Sudanese more often disagreed, potentially because Italy was not their preferred destination.
- At the same time, respondents more often agreed that smugglers misled them about the journey, despite having helped them.

4.3.13 Financing the journey: sources

- Most people financed their journey either through own funds or through the support of the family. Borrowing money was also quite common, especially among Bangladeshis (42%). Some were obliged to sell their assets to pay for the journey.
- Women from West Africa had frequently not paid anything at the beginning of their journey, whereas men more often used their own funds.
- For most people, especially from Sudan and West Africa, this was not enough money for the journey. They generally worked, or asked friends and families to raise funds for the rest of the journey (see next page, although caution should be taken with small sample sizes).

4.3.14 Challenges *en route*

Figure 100. How have you paid for the journey since then?

Question is multiselect

4.3.15 Information pre-departure

Figure 101. Did you obtain information before your journey?

Figure 102. Did you obtain information during your journey?

- A majority of respondents report that they did not obtain information before the journey.
- For those who did, the most frequent sources were friends and family (both in country of departure and elsewhere), followed by smugglers for all but Sudanese who mostly relied on online community/network (42%)

During the journey, over half of Bangladeshi and West Africans continued not to access to information (69% and 67%), followed by Pakistanis (54%). In contrast, 67% of Sudanese had accessed information.

4.3.16 Information post-departure

Figure 103. Source of information during journey

Reliance on family/friends decreases significantly after departure, probably because during the journey migrants and refugees prefer or have better access to “first-hand” information from other migrants and smugglers.

4.3.17 Means of information before and during the journey

Figure 104. Means of information before journey

Before the journey, West Africans, Bangladeshi and Pakistanis heavily rely on in-person conversation and phone calls. For Sudanese, in-person conversation is also relevant means of information (42%) after social media and messaging (49%).

Figure 105. Means of information during journey

Questions are multiselect

During the journey, in-person conversation become by far the most relevant means of information. Sudanese continue relying also on social media (28%), while for Pakistanis, West Africans and Bangladeshi another key mean is phone calls, as before the journey.

4.3.18 Reliability of information

- For West Africans (40%) and Sudanese (61%), other migrants by far are the most reliable sources of information, while Pakistanis considered other migrants and smugglers equally reliable, suggesting smugglers play a different role for different communities. Friends and family are not considered most reliable by many.
- A minority of West African, Pakistani and Bangladeshi respondents would have started this journey knowing what they know now. In contrast, a majority (59%) of Sudanese would do so.

4.3.19 Effects of Covid-19 on migration

Figure 108. How Covid-19 has affected life and migration experience?

The majority of respondents do not believe that Covid-19 had a direct impact on their migration experience. Some mentioned it made the journey more difficult due to border restrictions. This might mean that Covid-19 while is perceived as an additional challenge during the migration journey it doesn't substantially affecting decisions related to the journey.

4.3.20 Routes and conditions⁴

Map 3. Routes taken, including main stops, along the Central Mediterranean Route

⁴ For the routes and protection analysis of the data collected in Italy, MMC focused on movements along the Central Mediterranean route (CMR). Therefore, from the total sample of Bangladeshi interviewed in Italy (n=109), the analysis only considered those respondents who took the CMR to reach Italy (n=65).

4.3.21 Routes and conditions – reasons for stopping

Figure 109. West Africans Reasons for stopping per location

Figure 110. Sudanese reasons for stopping per location

Figure 111. Bangladeshi reasons for stopping per location

- The vast majority of respondents (96%) started the migration journey from their origin country.
- Almost all (98%) West African respondents transited Libya, 79% transited Niger, 32% Burkina Faso, and 31% Mali, with fewer transiting Algeria (20%) and Senegal (10%).
- In the case of Sudanese respondents, almost all (98%) reported transiting Libya, with a minority first crossing through Chad (36%) or Egypt (16%).
- Some 41% of West African respondents indicated that they chose the route because they saw it as their only option, 36% because their smuggler chose it, and 17% because friends or family suggested it or were taking it.
- Among Sudanese little over half (56%) chose their route because it was seen as the only option, 22% because it was the fastest, and 14% because their smuggler chose it.
- Bangladeshi respondents take a very different journey, and 97% flew for at least part of it. All transit Libya, 69% travelled via the United Arab Emirates, 29% via India, 26% via Egypt and 14% via Turkey, with smaller numbers transiting other countries in the Middle East and North Africa.
- The most frequently cited reasons for stopping along the journey were waiting for transport, working to earn money to cover the costs of further legs of the journey, looking for smugglers to organize the next stretch of the journey, being detained, and resting. However, the reasons for stopping appear linked to a number of factors, including the country of origin and gender of the respondents and the location in which they stopped

4.3.22 Protection: risks and perpetrators

Figure 112. Perceived risks along the CMR reported by West Africans respondents, by country / area

	n	Death	Physical violence	Sexual violence	Detention	Kidnaping	Robbery	Bribery/ extortion	Injury / ill health / conditions	Non-physical violence	Other
Mali	21	62%	71%	5%	29%	38%	43%	29%	0%	10%	10%
Niger	91	52%	49%	14%	22%	34%	40%	18%	0%	8%	5%
Algeria	34	35%	62%	3%	32%	24%	44%	21%	0%	3%	9%
Sahara Desert	70	86%	44%	17%	19%	34%	29%	10%	3%	6%	6%
Libya	517	71%	81%	40%	70%	48%	46%	24%	0%	14%	1%
Mediterranean Sea	231	99%	9%	0%	0%	1%	1%	0%	0%	0%	2%

Note: 'Refused' were 1% or lower, except for Niger (3%).

Figure 113. Perceived risks along the CMR reported by Sudanese respondents, by country / area

	n	Death	Physical violence	Sexual violence	Detention	Kidnaping	Robbery	Bribery/ extortion	Injury / ill health / conditions	Non-physical violence	Other
Sahara Desert	12	83%	42%	0%	17%	42%	42%	0%	58%	0%	0%
Libya	96	70%	88%	3%	67%	45%	13%	14%	1%	0%	4%
Mediterranean Sea	49	98%	4%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%

Note: Refused were all below 1%.

Figure 114. Perceived risks along the CMR reported by Bangladeshi respondents, by country / area

area	n	Death	Physical violence	Sexual violence	Detention	Kidnaping	Robbery	Bribery/ extortion	Injury / ill health / conditions	Non-physical violence	Other
Libya	62	39%	74%	8%	69%	47%	53%	68%	13%	11%	3%
Mediterranean Sea	38	92%	8%	0%	0%	0%	3%	0%	5%	0%	5%

Note: Refused were all 1% or below.

Figure 115. Perceived perpetrators of abuse and violations on the CMR reported by West African respondents, by country / area

	n	Criminals /criminal gangs	Armed groups/ militias	Smugglers	Government officials	Other migrants	Local people	Family members	Other	Don't know
Mali	21	38%	52%	24%	29%	5%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Niger	91	43%	34%	52%	36%	10%	2%	0%	0%	3%
Algeria	34	50%	29%	29%	44%	9%	1%	0%	0%	3%
Sahara Desert	70	33%	29%	60%	23%	6%	0%	0%	0%	3%
Libya	517	65%	63%	46%	51%	12%	4%	0%	1%	4%
Mediterranean Sea	231	9%	6%	39%	37%	7%	0%	0%	0%	9%

Note: Refused all below 1%.

Figure 116. Perceived perpetrators of abuse and violations on the CMR reported by Sudanese respondents, by country / area

	n	Criminals /criminal gangs	Armed groups/ militias	Smugglers	Government officials	Other migrants	Local people	Family members	Other	Don't know
Sahara Desert	12	50%	17%	25%	8%	0%	0%	0%	0%	8%
Libya	96	84%	36%	67%	6%	1%	2%	0%	1%	1%
Mediterranean Sea	49	10%	2%	82%	2%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%

Note: 'Refused' all below 1%.

Figure 117. Perceived perpetrators of abuse and violations on the CMR reported by Bangladeshi respondents, by country / area

	n	Criminals /criminal gangs	Armed groups/ militias	Smugglers	Government officials	Other migrants	Local people	Family members	Other	Don't know
Libya	62	63%	35%	29%	44%	5%	3%	0%	0%	3%
Mediterranean Sea	38	0%	3%	26%	24%	0%	0%	0%	0%	11%

Note: 'Refused' at 3% for Libya and 5% for Mediterranean Sea.

4.3.23 Protection: dangerous locations

Map 4. Dangerous locations on the Central Mediterranean Route, as perceived by 4Mi respondents

- All respondents crossed the Mediterranean, which was reported as dangerous by 42% of West African respondents, 49% of Sudanese respondents and 58% of Bangladeshi respondents. 98% of respondents transited Libya, where Tripoli is most often reported to be dangerous by all three groups. Among West Africans, the towns of Sabha and Sabratha are also commonly cited, while Sudanese name Bani Walid and Benghazi, though to a lesser extent. Locations in other countries are less frequently reported as dangerous, even when allowing for the smaller number of people travelling through them. In addition to Tripoli, Bangladeshis also reported Benghazi as dangerous. The Sahara Desert, if we sum reports both of the Sahara as being dangerous as well as specific locations within the Sahara, is more frequently reported as dangerous than the Mediterranean Sea or Libya.
- West Africans report numerous dangers along the CMR. Libya was reported to pose dangers of physical violence, death, and detention; and the risk of sexual violence is more frequently reported there than in other locations. Death in the Mediterranean was reported as a risk by almost all respondents, and the perceived risk of death in the Sahara is also very high, with other risks also reported there. Mali, Niger, and Algeria are reportedly less dangerous, but many respondents still fear physical violence and death in those countries, although the small sample sizes for Mali and Algeria demand caution in interpretation.
- Women from West Africa far more frequently report a risk of sexual violence than men: 83%, making it the second most common risk reported by women. For all other kinds of incident, men and women reported types of risk in the same order: physical violence (83% of men and 84% of women); death (77% men and 63% women); detention (75% men and 60% women), kidnapping (51% men and 43% women) and robbery (53% men and 31% women).
- Among Sudanese, despite not always taking the same route through the Sahara or Libya, or across the Mediterranean, perceived risks were similar, and dominated by a fear of death, followed by physical violence and detention in Libya, and injury or ill-health crossing the Sahara (again, caution should be taken given small sample size).
- Of the Bangladeshis who indicated dangerous locations in Libya (95%), less than half considered they were at risk of death, but a large majority mentioned physical violence and detention, as well as bribery/extortion. Almost all considered the Mediterranean to pose a risk of death.
- Reports of sexual violence as a risk are very low among the Bangladeshi and Sudanese respondents, likely because such risks are more commonly reported by women, and all these respondents are men.
- The perceived perpetrators of abuse vary. In Libya, West African respondents consider criminal gangs and armed groups to be mostly responsible, followed by government officials and then smugglers. In Mali it is most often armed groups, while in Algeria it is criminal gangs (note the small sample size in both cases). In Niger—just before crossing the Sahara—and in the Sahara, most respondents consider smugglers to be the main perpetrators of abuse. On the Mediterranean, fewer indicate a culprit, but smugglers and officials are mentioned. A larger proportion (84%) of Sudanese respondents considered criminal gangs and smugglers to be the main perpetrators of abuses in Libya. Libya was also the country with the highest percentage of mentions of criminal gangs as perceived perpetrators of risk among Bangladeshis (63%). Smugglers appear to be considered less of a threat among Bangladeshis (29%), and militias had a similar score (35%). However, particularly in the case of Libya, respondents might not always be able to distinguish clearly between criminal gangs, militias, and smugglers, as criminal gangs and militias might be involved in smuggling, and smugglers involved in other criminal activities.

5. Key findings

This analysis seeks to provide a better understanding of the journey of refugees and migrants travelling along mixed migration routes towards Europe, including their experiences along the route, the risks they face, the challenges they encounter but also their motivations for moving, and future intentions. The aim of the analysis is to provide a strong evidence base, to inform policy makers on how to enhance EU migration governance, taking into account the protection needs of people on the move.

Overall, 4Mi data reveal how drivers of migration for refugees and migrants interviewed in Italy and Greece are varied and multiple. Violence-related drivers frequently intertwine with economic and personal factors. People flee conflict and violence, or flee because they are discriminated against, because of lack of personal prospects and/or professional opportunities in their country of origin or host country, because they want and need to provide for their families and themselves, and often for multiple reasons combined.

In their decision to migrate, 4Mi respondents are subject to different type of influences, with family and friends playing an important role, especially before departure, while relying mostly on others traveling ahead of them or smugglers once they are *en route*. Reliance on smugglers can increase refugees' and migrants' vulnerability as they have less control over the migration journey.

Journeys are risky and expensive. In terms of length, respondents surveyed in Italy mentioned traveling for an average of more than 2 years. In Greece, respondents reported an average length of journey of 4 months. During the journey, the majority of respondents transited at least two or three countries before reaching Europe. Several and competing factors contribute to the length of the journeys. One challenge is financial constraints, which often oblige people to stop and work to earn money to continue the journey. The lack of financial resource is likely to further increase migrants' vulnerability as people may fall into debt.

Migrants and refugees face a variety of protection risks on their journeys. Libya and Turkey were reported as particularly dangerous, with many respondents having been detained or faced physical and sexual abuse, especially women. While governmental authorities/police were most frequently perceived as perpetrators of protection incidents among people interviewed in Greece who travelled through Pakistan, Iran, Turkey and Greece, criminal gangs/militia were reported more often by people interviewed in Italy who travelled through Mali, Niger, Algeria and Libya. Smugglers also feature in both cases as perceived perpetrators of violations and abuse.

The challenges of the journey means that refugees and migrants need assistance. Respondents, especially those interviewed in Greece, frequently reported the need for psychological support and medical assistance. Legal assistance is often needed in both Italy and Greece, which might speak to respondents' need to regularize their status in order to avoid further protection risks or to seek integration through education or job.

Covid-19 and related measures seem to have played a very different role depending on the country of interview. The majority of respondents interviewed in Italy do not believe that Covid-19 had a direct impact on their migration experience other than making the journey more difficult due to border restrictions. Conversely, people interviewed in Greece, in addition to constraints caused by border controls, more often reported other type of limitations such as exhaustion of financial resources or increased risks.